

Piercing the Corporate Veil: Legal Liability of Holding Companies for Their Subsidiaries

Introduction

Companies are well suited legal entities for attracting investors' capital and deploying it on a large scale¹. Additionally, they acquire legal personality where it can own property, become a party to a contract, can sue and be sued among others.

With globalization, business operations increasingly cross-national borders. The rise of free trade and open markets has created a global economy, pushing countries to offer incentives to attract businesses and boost economic growth². In this context, corporate group system has emerged due to the economic concentration processes undertaken by enterprises³, when a single, large, national or foreign company controls a group of companies with similar activities and imposes on them the obligation to adhere to a unified economic plan⁴.

The dominant company in these processes is known in English and American legal systems as the Holding company. While in the French system, it is known as the Parent company. Conversely, the company controlled by the Holding or Parent company is called the Subsidiary company⁵.

Therefore, an important legal issue arises from this structure: whether a Holding company can be held liable for the obligations of its Subsidiaries. Such liability contradicts the "universal bedrock principle" of company law: that each corporation has distinct legal personality and limited liability⁶. Traditionally, this means that a company cannot be held responsible for the debts or wrongful acts of another, even within the same corporate group⁷.

Nevertheless, some courts and scholars have recognized that exceptions to this rule, holding that under certain conditions, the Holding companies might be held accountable for the actions and obligations of its Subsidiaries.

¹Gary Gorton and Richard Rosen, Corporate Control Portfolio Choice and the Decline of Banking, The Warton School-University of Pennsylvania, July 1994, p.3.

²The Legal Framework of the Holding Company - According to Egyptian Law - An Analytical Study in Light of the Law on Public Business Sector No. 203 of 1991 and Its Executive Regulations, the Researcher Mustafa Nabil Dalati.

³The Legal Relationship Between the Holding Company and Its Subsidiaries (A Comparative Study), Ahmed Mahmoud Al-Mosaada, Al-Majma'ah University, College of Business Administration, Department of Law, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Published in the Journal of Social and Humanitarian Studies, Department of Economic and Legal Sciences, Issue 12, June 2014, p. 11.

⁴Holding Company Legal Concept and Formation Mechanism, Dr. Duraid Mahmoud Ali, Alasmarya University Journal, Volume 10, December 2008.

⁵The Legal Framework of the Holding Company - According to Egyptian Law - An Analytical Study in Light of the Law on Public Business Sector No. 203 of 1991 and Its Executive Regulations, the Researcher Mustafa Nabil Dalati

⁶The extension of Holding company liability in James Hardie industries PLC V White, Tom White; Martin Petrin and Barnali Choudhury "Group Company Liability", 2018, p.772.

⁷Adams v Cape Industries plc, 1990, Ch. 433, p.536.

In this research, we will discuss the principle of the corporate shield of corporate entities, and the situations where a Holding company may be held liable for its Subsidiary's obligations.

The General Principle of the Corporate Shield of Corporate Groups

For over 150 years, the principle of limited liability has been a fundamental feature of the companies. This principle, along with the concept of separate legal personality, distinguishes companies from the personalities of its shareholders and protects them from being personally liable for the company's debts and other obligations⁸. Together, these two principles form the so-called **corporate shield** or **the veil of incorporation**⁹.

The principle of the veil of incorporation in general is as opaque and impassable as an iron curtain¹⁰. The limited shareholder liability serves an important public policy—the policy of encouraging investment by limiting risks. A prospective investor, while willing to invest some assets and even considerable time and effort in a new venture, may be unwilling to accept the risk of losing certain other assets not involved in the venture. Therefore, in a society, which wishes to stimulate investment, it is not surprising that the law should sanction, at least to some degree, a device, which protects an investor against unlimited liability¹¹.

Additionally, this concept was confirmed by the House of lords in the landmark case **Salomon**¹², whose facts of are summarized in that Mr. Salomon sold his business to a company he set up, keeping most of the shares and becoming a secured creditor. When the company went bankrupt, he asked to be repaid first. The liquidator said the company was just Salomon in another form and should not be treated separately.

Nevertheless, the House of Lords disagreed, holding that the company is a separate legal entity from its members. Even though Salomon owned and controlled it, the company itself owns its assets and is solely responsible for its debts¹³.

Similarly, In **Industrial Equity Ltd**¹⁴, the High Court of Australia held that the principle of separate legal personality prevents a Holding company from treating the profits of its wholly owned Subsidiary as its own. Despite full ownership, the Subsidiary remains a distinct legal entity, and its assets and profits do not automatically belong to the Parent company.

⁸Cases & Materials on Company Law, 6th edition, A. Hicks, & S.H. Goo, New York: Oxford University Press. 2004.p1; Majority rule and minority protection in company law, E.A.Gregory, Elcoon, Press,1997.P.28; Hobart Bridge Co. Ltd. v. Federal Commissioner of Taxation, 1951; Gas Lighting Improvement Co Ltd v. Inland Revenue, United Kingdom House of Lords, 11 May 1923.

⁹The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p. 378.

¹⁰The principles of modern company law, L.C.B.Gower, Indiana University, 2011, P.66.

¹¹Piercing the the Corporate Veil—The Undercapitalization Factor, Harvey Gelb University of Wyoming College of Law, Chicago-Kent Law Review, Volume 59, Issue 1, Article 2, December 1982, p.1.

¹²Salomon v. Salomon & Co., 1897, A.C. 22.

¹³The legal executive: Institute of Legal Executives, R. Lewis, Volume 4, the University of California press, 2008, P.72.

¹⁴Industrial Equity Ltd v Blackburn, 137 CLR 567, 1977.

Moreover, the **Judge Templeman LJ** noted that English company law could lead to unusual results. He explained that a Holding company can create several Subsidiaries, all controlled by the same shareholders. If one of the Subsidiaries fails and goes bankrupt, the Holding company and the other Subsidiaries can continue doing well, and the shareholders benefit without being responsible for the debts of the failed Subsidiary¹⁵.

Accordingly, the case laws and jurists reinforce the long-standing rule that each company in a corporate group is legally separate, and even a 100% shareholding does not dissolve that separation. It confirms that the principle of separate corporate personality remains a fundamental and authoritative doctrine in company law¹⁶.

Piercing the Corporate Veil and Expanding Holding Company Liability

Although the separation of legal personality encourages business growth and protects investors, there are situations, in which courts decide to disregard the corporate entity or, in other words, pierce the corporate veil. One familiar generalization descriptive of this phenomenon states that “when the notion of legal entity is used to defeat public convenience, justify wrong, protect fraud, or defend crime, the law will regard the corporation as an association of persons”¹⁷. Similarly, another court has observed that “the doctrine of ‘piercing the corporate veil’ is invoked to prevent fraud or to achieve equity”¹⁸.

I. From Formal Structure to Substantive Reality in Veil Piercing

Economists have long known that limited liability can cause problems and leads to injustice and serious consequences ¹⁹. Thus, to reduce these problems, courts sometimes allow creditors to pierce (or lift) the corporate veil, meaning they disregard the company’s separate legal personality and look at the individuals who actually control the company. If plaintiffs meet certain criteria, they can overcome limited liability and hold shareholders, including Holding companies, responsible for damages. This principle is commonly known as **piercing the corporate veil**²⁰.

¹⁵The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p. 376.

¹⁶The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p. 378.

¹⁷United States v. Milwaukee Refrigerator Transit Co., 1905, 142 F. 247, 255, C.C.E.D. Wis.

¹⁸Bartle v. Home Owners Coop. Inc., 1955; quoting International Aircraft Trading Co. v. Manufacturers Trust Co., 1948.

¹⁹The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p. 377.

²⁰Meredith Dearborn, Enterprise Liability: Reviewing and Revitalizing Liability for Corporate Groups, 97 CAL. L. REV., 2009, p.203,204; Gwynne Skinner, Rethinking Limited Liability of Parent Corporations for Foreign Subsidiaries’ Violations of International Human Rights Law, Washington and Lee Law Review, Fall 9-1-2015, p.1796.

While the landmark case of **Salomon** established the foundational principle that a company is legally distinct from its shareholders²¹, many judicial decisions have held that the separate legal personality of a company is not an absolute principle. The early signs of the piercing doctrine appeared in the case of **Smith, Stone & Knight**²², where the court sought to establish criteria for piercing the corporate veil, particularly regarding the question of whether a Subsidiary company with its own legal personality could be considered separate from its Holding company. The court outlined several factors to determine when veil piercing is justified, including:

- a. Whether the profits made actually belong to the Holding company.
- b. Whether the person managing the company was appointed by the Holding company.
- c. Whether the Holding company was the mastermind behind the business venture.
- d. Whether the Holding company made the key decisions, including setting the capital of the business.
- e. Whether the company's profits were generated by its own skill and management.
- f. Whether the company was under the actual and continuous control of the Holding company.

Moreover, **Lord denning in Littlewoods mail order stores Ltd.**²³, explained that courts may, in certain circumstances, lift the veil of incorporation to hold shareholders or Parent companies personally liable for the company's obligations effectively "removing the mask" to reveal the underlying reality behind the corporate structure²⁴. Similarly, in **Lazarus Estates Ltd**²⁵, he emphasized that the corporate form cannot be used as a shield for fraud or injustice. He affirmed that the veil may be pierced when the company is used as a façade to conceal the truth or to evade legal responsibilities, famously stating that "fraud unravels everything."²⁶

In addition, **Easterbrook and Fischel**²⁷ have pointed out that successful cases of piercing the veil usually involve companies with close Holding-Subsidiary relationships²⁸. While Holding companies are generally shielded from the liabilities of their Subsidiaries, this protection is not absolute. In certain circumstances, a Holding company may exercise such extensive control that

²¹Piercing the Corporate Veil in Australia, Ramsay, Ian M & and Noakes David B, 19 Company and Securities Law Journal 250-271, 2001, p. 2.

²²Smith, Stone & Knight v. Birmingham Corporation, 1939; Piercing the Limited Liability of the Sole Shareholder in a Single-Member Company: A Comparative Study, Reem Anwar Ahmed Raslan, Faculty of Law, Cairo University, p.4796.

²³Littlewoods Mail Order Stores Ltd. v. IRC, 1969.

²⁴Enterprise Liability: Reviewing and Revitalizing Liability for Corporate Groups, Meredith Dearborn 97 CAL. L. REV.,2009, p.203,204; Gwynne Skinner, Rethinking Limited Liability of Parent Corporations for Foreign Subsidiaries' Violations of International Human Rights Law, Washington and Lee Law Review, Fall 9-1-2015, p.1796

²⁵Lazarus Estates Ltd v Beasley [1956] 1 QB 702.

²⁶Lifting, Piercing, and Sidestepping the Corporate Veil, James Wibberley, Guildhall Chambers & Michelle Di Gioia, Gardner Leader, 2013, pt.5; piercing the Limited Liability of the Sole Shareholder in a Single-Member Company: A Comparative Study, Reem Anwar Ahmed Raslan, Faculty of Law, Cairo University, p.4797.

²⁷Limited liability and the corporation, Easterbrook, Frank H and Daniel R Fischel, The University of Chicago Law Review, 1985, p, 89.

²⁸Our two corporation systems: Law and economics, Manne, Henry G, 53 Virginia Law Review, 1967, p 259; A skeptical view of financialized corporate governance, Admati, Anat R, The Journal of Economic Perspectives 2017, pp131, 132; The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p. 377.

the Subsidiary effectively becomes a mere instrument for carrying out the Holding company's illicit objectives²⁹.

Consequently, Courts may lift the corporate veil in several situations to achieve justice and prevent circumvention of law. In doing so, the courts consider several factors³⁰ including:

- a. The case when a company's money and assets are mixed together with those of its shareholders, and payments between the company, its shareholders, or others are not clear or well documented, it becomes hard to tell which funds belong to the company and which belong to the shareholders³¹. This confusion breaks the idea that the company is a separate legal entity and can be a reason for the court to hold the shareholders personally responsible for the company's debts.
- b. The situation when formal corporate procedures are not followed, making it difficult for third parties dealing with the company to clearly identify the other contracting party. As a result, there is confusion or ambiguity regarding the identity of the company or the individual acting on its behalf in contractual relationships³².
- c. Undercapitalization³³, when a company lacks sufficient funds to operate effectively or meet its legal obligations, either because its required capital has not been fully paid (nominal undercapitalization) or because it does not have enough money to cover its debts (actual undercapitalization). Although some laws impose minimum capital requirements for limited liability companies to ensure financial stability and protect creditors, undercapitalization alone does not justify piercing the corporate veil. Courts typically require additional evidence, such as intentional misconduct by controlling shareholders who deliberately withhold capital to evade legal responsibilities, before holding individuals personally liable.
- d. Whether the Holding dominates the Subsidiary's decision-making or whether there is confusion of affairs, and management personnel of the company and its shareholder³⁴.

²⁹The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p. 396; *Cebu Shipyard and Engineering Works, Inc. v. William Lines, Inc.*, 1999.

³⁰Piercing the Corporate Veil: Focusing the Inquiry, Cathy S. Krendl & James R. Krendl, 55 *Denv. L.J.* 1, 16–17, 1978, listing Frederick J. Powell's published indicators that a Subsidiary is a mere instrumentality at 13 n.40, David H. Barber, *Piercing the Corporate Veil*, 17 *Willamette L. Rev.*, 1980, p.374–375.

³¹Piercing the Corporate Veil: Historical, Theoretical & Comparative Perspectives, Cheng-Han Tan, Jiangyu Wang, Christian Hofmann, 2019, P.180-181; Piercing the Limited Liability of the Sole Shareholder in a Single-Member Company: A Comparative Study, Reem Anwar Ahmed Raslan, Faculty of Law, Cairo University, p.4790; BGH II ZR 178/03, Nov. 14, 2005, 2006 NZG 350.

³²Limited Liability: A Legal and Economic Analysis by Edward Elgar Publishing, 2016, Bainbridge, Stephen M. & Henderson, M. Todd, p. 280.

³³Piercing the Corporate Veil: Historical, Theoretical & Comparative Perspectives, Cheng-Han Tan, Jiangyu Wang, Christian Hofmann (2019), P.191; Limited Liability: A Legal and Economic Analysis by Edward Elgar Publishing, 2016, Bainbridge, Stephen M. & Henderson, M. Todd, p.180-182.

³⁴The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p. 397; Piercing the Corporate Veil: An Empirical Study, Robert B. Thompson, 76 *CORNELL L. REV.*, 1991, p.1064; Piercing the Corporate Veil: Historical, Theoretical & Comparative Perspectives, Cheng-Han Tan, Jiangyu Wang, Christian Hofmann (2019), P.192.

II. Judicial Doctrines Supporting Veil Piercing

Many doctrines have emerged across various legal systems worldwide that justify piercing the corporate veil. These doctrines provide a rationale for looking beyond the company's separate legal personality, especially when that structure is misused to evade obligations or facilitate wrongful conduct. The following sections will explore key justifications for piercing the corporate veil, supported by illustrative examples:

i. Fraud and Façade doctrine

This principle provides a recognized basis for piercing the corporate veil when a company, or one of its Subsidiaries, is created or used as a mere façade to conceal fraudulent conduct or evade legal obligations. In such cases, the doctrine of separate legal personality cannot be invoked to perpetrate fraud or mislead creditors and the courts may disregard its independent legal identity and hold those behind it directly accountable³⁵.

Unlike the "single economic unit" argument, courts are more willing to pierce the veil on this ground. It is widely accepted by the courts that the veil may be lifted where it is proven that a company is nothing more than a façade concealing the true facts³⁶.

In the **Cape case**, the claimants argued that the U.S. Subsidiaries, CPC and AMC, were used by Cape as tools to avoid liability for asbestos injuries while continuing business in the United States. The Court of Appeal agreed that the Subsidiaries were set up to carry on Cape's asbestos trade, but it rejected the claim that they were sham companies. The court explained that the Subsidiaries could not simply be treated as Cape itself, since the claimants had not shown any illegal purpose in creating them. Cape's actions were seen only as a restructuring of its marketing through new Subsidiaries, which did not meet the test for the "**Fraud and Façade**" principle. There was no actual or potential illegality³⁷, and the court could not find anything unlawful in **Cape** arrangement of its affairs.

In contrast, in **Gilford Motor**³⁸, the court pierced the corporate veil because the company was used as a sham to evade a legal obligation, effectively amounting to fraud or improper conduct³⁹. Similarly, In **Jones v Lipman**⁴⁰, the defendant tried to avoid transferring land by transferring it to a company he controlled, effectively using the company as a device to evade a specific

³⁵Francisco Motors Corporation v. CA, 1999; Nick Corp. v. JNS Aviation, Inc. (In Re JNS AVIATION, LLC), United States Bankruptcy Court, N.D. Texas, Amarillo Division, 2007; Velarde v. Lopez, Inc., 2004.

³⁶The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p. 405; Payne, 'Lifting the Corporate Veil: A Reassessment of the Fraud Exception'⁵⁶ Cambridge Law Journal (1997), p 284, 290.

³⁷Corporate Liability Towards Tort Victims in the Personal Injury Context, Xue Feng, thesis, Queen Mary University of London, June 2017, p.70; The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p. 406.

³⁸Gilford Motor Co Ltd v Horne, 1933.

³⁹Piercing the Limited Liability of the Sole Shareholder in a Single-Member Company: A Comparative Study, Reem Anwar Ahmed Raslan, Faculty of Law, Cairo University, p.4798;The New Law of Piercing the Corporate Veil in the UK, Alexander Schall, 2016, p.545-555.

⁴⁰Jones v Lipman, 1962.

performance order. The court pierced the corporate veil, holding that the company was a mere façade created to conceal the defendant's wrongdoing. Both cases, demonstrate the court's willingness to disregard the corporate form when it is used to frustrate legal obligations through sham or evasion.

For that reason, some commentators argue that misrepresentation can justify piercing the corporate veil because forces creditors to spend excessive time and money checking the company's true situation⁴¹. For instance, if a Holding company claims a Subsidiary is independent while actually controlling it, creditors may be forced to investigate both companies, leading to unnecessary costs. Veil piercing helps prevent this kind of waste.

Moreover, the Australian judge **Jenkinson J**⁴² stated that "the separate legal personality of a company is to be disregarded only if the court can see that there is, in fact or in law, a partnership between companies in a group, or that there is a cover-up in which that company is playing a role, or that the creation or use of the company was designed to enable a legal obligation or a trust to be evaded or a fraud to be perpetrated."

Thus, the most compelling justification for a misrepresentation-based exception to limited liability may lie in a combination of the doctrine of **Estoppel** and what one commentator describes as the ideals of **Truth and Respect** that should govern a debtor's relationship with its creditors⁴³. Estoppel operates on the premise that when a shareholder expressly or implicitly represents personal responsibility for corporate debts, and a creditor reasonably relies on that representation, the shareholder should be precluded from denying such liability⁴⁴. The ideal of **Truth** requires the corporate debtor to be truthful and honest in its dealing with its creditors, and the ideal of **Respect** requires that creditors' claims be given priority, particularly when the corporation transfers its assets⁴⁵. Together, these principles support a limited but meaningful basis for piercing the corporate veil in cases of misrepresentation.

ii. The Instrumentally Doctrine

This approach has been adopted by the U.S. judiciary to pierce the corporate veil⁴⁶. This doctrine was explained in the case of **Lowendahl**⁴⁷, where the court set out three conditions for piercing the corporate veil:

- a. The plaintiff must show that the shareholders had total control over the company.
- b. That control was used to commit fraud, dishonesty, or illegal acts that harmed the plaintiff.

⁴¹The Rights of Creditors of Affiliated Corporations, Richard A. Posner, 1976, p.520–521.

⁴²1988, ALR 267 FC, Woodward, Jenkinson and Foster JJ; The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p.397.

⁴³The Duties of the Corporate Debtor to Its Creditors, Robert Charles Clark, 509–511, 1977.

⁴⁴The Principles of Modern Company Law, L.C.B. Gower, K.W. Wedder-burn et al. eds., 3d ed., 1969, p.381–383.

⁴⁵Robert Charles Clark, the Duties of the Corporate Debtor to Its Creditors, 90, 1977, Harv. L. Rev. 505, 509–511.

⁴⁶Piercing the Limited Liability of the Sole Shareholder in a Single-Member Company: A Comparative Study, Reem Anwar Ahmed Raslan, Faculty of Law, Cairo University, p.4802.

⁴⁷Lowendahl v. Baltimore & Ohio Railroad Co., 1936; Piercing the Limited Liability of the Sole Shareholder in a Single-Member Company: A Comparative Study, Reem Anwar Ahmed Raslan, Faculty of Law, Cairo University, p.4805.

c. The plaintiff must have suffered a loss because of those wrongful acts⁴⁸.

For the first condition, control means more than just managing the company's money, it must be so complete that the company has no independent will, and simply follows the orders of the person in control⁴⁹. But control alone, without satisfying the other elements, is insufficient to justify piercing the corporate veil⁵⁰.

Moreover, this principle was demonstrated in the case of **Zaist**⁵¹, where the court emphasized that control alone is not sufficient grounds for piercing the corporate veil. There must be additional factors showing that the company was merely an instrumentality of the shareholders; for example, the shareholders' control over the company's finances and policies to such an extent that the company has no independent will and acts solely as a tool of the shareholders. Furthermore, the defendant must have committed acts that involve a breach of law, violation of legal duties, unlawful conduct, or fraud, resulting in harm to the plaintiff.

In **Zaist**⁵², the court held that control alone - typically evidenced by the defendant owning a large share of the company's stock or holding significant managerial positions - is not sufficient grounds for piercing the corporate veil. Control must be so extensive that the company lacks independence from the defendant and functions merely as an instrumentality or alter ego of that person.

Similarly, In **Arnold**⁵³, the court addressed the issue of piercing the corporate veil, emphasizing that mere ownership or control of a corporation by an individual is not sufficient to disregard the company's separate legal identity. The court held that veil piercing requires evidence that the corporation was used as a mere instrumentality or Alter ego to perpetrate fraud, injustice, or wrongdoing, resulting in harm to the plaintiff. This case reinforced the principle that courts must look beyond formalities to prevent abuse of the corporate structure when used to shield improper conduct.

However, it is important to note that the **Alter-Ego Theory** and the **Instrumentality Doctrine** share many similarities. Both require the existence of some wrongdoing resulting from control over the company, to the extent that the company cannot function as a separate legal entity. In fact, the court in **Wm. Passalacqua Builders, Inc.**⁵⁴ stated that there is no clear distinction between these two standards and that one may be used interchangeably with the other.

⁴⁸Limited Liability: A Legal and Economic Analysis by Edward Elgar, 2016, Bainbridge, Stephen M. & Henderson, M. Todd , p.118-119.

⁴⁹Cheng-Han Tan, Jiangyu Wang, Christian Hofmann, 2019, P.160.

⁵⁰Limited Liability: A Legal and Economic Analysis by Edward Elgar Publishing, 2016, Bainbridge, Stephen M. & Henderson, M. Todd, p.119.

⁵¹Zaist v. Olson, 7 Ill. App. 3d 1066, 1972.

⁵²Piercing the Limited Liability of the Sole Shareholder in a Single-Member Company: A Comparative Study, Reem Anwar Ahmed Raslan, Faculty of Law, Cairo University, p.4806.

⁵³Arnold v. Phillips, 117 F.2d 497, 502, 5th Cir., 1941.

⁵⁴Wm. Passalacqua Builders, Inc. v. Resnick Developers South, Inc., 933 F.2d 131, 138, 2nd Cir., 1991; Piercing the Corporate Veil: Historical, Theoretical & Comparative Perspectives, Cheng-Han Tan, Jiangyu Wang, Christian Hofmann, 2019, P.161.

iii. The Alter-Ego Theory

This approach has been also adopted by the U.S. judiciary to pierce the corporate veil⁵⁵. This theory can be defined as the situation where the court finds that the company has no independent existence apart from its partner, whether that partner is a natural or legal person. This results in unfair consequences for the company's creditors. When these conditions are met, the court may order piercing the corporate veil and hold the partners personally liable for the company's debts⁵⁶.

One of the key indicators of disregarding a company's separate legal personality is the failure to provide it with sufficient capital to carry out the business for which it was established. This may be accompanied by non-compliance with essential procedural rules. Additional signs include failing to maintain proper corporate records, not distributing profits in accordance with legal requirements, and disregarding the statutory rules governing the management and operation of the company⁵⁷.

Generally, for the principle of piercing the corporate veil to apply, there must be an overlap between the identity of the partner and the company, such that they effectively operate as a single unit, leading to unjust outcomes. Moreover, courts in many U.S. states do not require proof of fraud as a condition for piercing the veil⁵⁸.

In **Walkovsky**⁵⁹, which concerns the determination of liability and the application of the corporate veil piercing doctrine under U.S. law. The defendant was the sole owner of several taxi companies and insured them only up to the legal minimum. When one of his taxis was involved in an accident that injured the plaintiff, the plaintiff argued that all the companies were essentially a single entity and that the defendant had structured them in this way to deceive the public. The New York Appellate Court, ruled that while the primary purpose of corporations is to promote commerce through the protection of limited liability, this protection is not absolute. The court may pierce the corporate veil in cases involving fraud or to achieve justice, particularly where a shareholder uses the corporate form as a mere façade for personal dealings. In such cases, the court may apply the doctrine of **Respondeat superior**⁶⁰, which extends to both contractual and tortious liability.

The court distinguished between structuring a group of companies in a certain way to benefit from limited liability - which in itself does not justify piercing the corporate veil - and situations where there is an overlap between the partner's identity and that of the company, such as when

⁵⁵Piercing the Limited Liability of the Sole Shareholder in a Single-Member Company: A Comparative Study, Reem Anwar Ahmed Raslan, Faculty of Law, Cairo University, p.4801.

⁵⁶Legal Information Institute, Cornell Law School.

⁵⁷ *Fletcher v. Atex, Inc.*, 68 F.3d 1451, 1995, p. 4.

⁵⁸Piercing the Limited Liability of the Sole Shareholder in a Single-Member Company: A Comparative Study, Reem Anwar Ahmed Raslan, Faculty of Law, Cairo University, p.4803.

⁵⁹*Walkovszky v. Carlton*, New York Court of Appeals, 18 N.Y.2d 414, 1966.

⁶⁰*Respondeat superior* is a legal doctrine in which an employer is held legally responsible for the wrongful acts of their employees, provided those acts occur within the scope of their employment.

the partner mixes personal funds with company funds. The latter case may form a valid basis for piercing the corporate veil⁶¹.

Moreover, the court clarified that mere control over a corporation is insufficient; there must also be conduct that produces unjust outcomes⁶². This idea was invoked in **RRX Industries Inc.**⁶³, where the court held that the **Alter-Ego Doctrine** applies when:

- a. There is such unity of interest and ownership that the separate personalities of the individual and the corporation no longer exist; and
- b. An inequitable result would follow if the acts were treated as those of the corporation alone.

Although these are often described as separate requirements, they both focus on whether someone misused control so much that the company was no longer acting as an independent business. In such cases, the court may ignore the company's legal status if it was being used as a cover for fraud or improper behavior⁶⁴.

Additionally, some U.S. courts have distinguished between veil piercing and Alter-ego theory. In veil-piercing cases, liability is indirect and based on the application of Respondeat superior principles—holding shareholders liable as if they were principals for the acts of their corporate "agents." In contrast, cases involving alter-ego treat the company and the shareholder as one and the same, resulting in direct personal liability for the shareholder⁶⁵.

Finally, some legal scholars have argued that there is an additional basis for piercing the corporate veil in U.S. law, known as the "**Enhanced Alter-ego theory**". This approach requires, besides the intertwining of identities, the presence of another element, such as: fraud or the achievement of outcomes that are contrary to justice. This doctrine has been embraced by the courts in many states⁶⁶.

iv. The Agency Doctrine

In corporate groups, a Subsidiary may sometimes act as an agent for its Holding company, making the Holding liable for the Subsidiary's actions. However, establishing such an agency is difficult and assessed on a case-by-case basis⁶⁷.

Typically, an agency is formed by a contract concluded between two parties, although it is not always contractual in nature. A principal-agent relationship can only be created if both parties

⁶¹Limited Liability: A Legal and Economic Analysis by Edward Elgar Publishing, 2016, Bainbridge, Stephen M. & Henderson, M. Todd, p.106; Piercing the Limited Liability of the Sole Shareholder in a Single-Member Company: A Comparative Study, Reem Anwar Ahmed Raslan, Faculty of Law, Cairo University, p.4804.

⁶²Limited Liability: A Legal and Economic Analysis by Edward Elgar Publishing, 2016, Bainbridge, Stephen M. & Henderson, M. Todd, p.106-109; Piercing the Limited Liability of the Sole Shareholder in a Single-Member Company: A Comparative Study, Reem Anwar Ahmed Raslan, Faculty of Law, Cairo University, p.4804.

⁶³RRX Indus, Inc. v. Lab-Con, Inc, 772 F.2d 543, 545, 9th Cir. 1985.

⁶⁴Sabine Towing & Transportation Co, Inc v. Merit Ventures, Inc, 575 F.Supp. 1442, 1446, E.D. Tex., 1983.

⁶⁵Int'l Union, UAW v. Aguirre, 410 F.3d 297, 2005.

⁶⁶Limited Liability: A Legal and Economic Analysis by Edward Elgar Publishing, 2016, Bainbridge, Stephen M. & Henderson, M. Todd, p.115-119.

⁶⁷The Decision of the Supreme Court in VTB v Nutritek' 19 Trusts & Trustees, Davies D, 2013, p.200.

agree to it. Courts have held that this agreement may be explicit or implied through the parties' actions, even if they do not label the relationship as agency or explicitly deny it. What matters is that both parties, through words or behavior, demonstrate mutual agreement that one is acting on behalf of the other⁶⁸.

Agency should be seen as different from veil piercing⁶⁹. In an agency relationship, the agent is still a separate person from the principal. The principal is responsible for the agent's actions only because they gave permission and the agent acted as instructed⁷⁰.

In **Cape Industries**⁷¹, the Court of Appeal in England rejected the plaintiffs' argument that Cape's Subsidiaries (NAAC and CPC) were acting as agents for the Holding company. The court found that⁷²:

- a. Both NAAC and CPC conducted business independently in the U.S., had their own profits, paid taxes, had separate creditors and debtors, and were not merely extensions of Cape.
- b. Cape did not control the day-to-day operations of the Subsidiaries. They had freedom to engage in other business activities and did so.

However, Courts have now become more likely to disregard the separate legal personality of a company, particularly in the case of small or closely-held companies. They appear more open to applying agency principles, especially where the Holding company exercises such complete control that the Subsidiary can properly be regarded as merely an agent of the shareholder⁷³.

In short, it is still uncertain whether a Holding company can be held responsible through agency. Courts need clear proof that the Subsidiary was actually acting on behalf of the Holding, not just influenced by it. Because the rules about agency are not clear and vary from case to case, it is hard to predict the success of such claims⁷⁴.

v. The Single Economic Unit Doctrine

Some judges reject misuse of the group structure and emphasize the need to distinguish cases involving corporate groups from those involving individual shareholders⁷⁵. The single economic

⁶⁸Garnac Grain Co. Inc. v. H.M.F. Faure Fairclough Ltd., issued 1968, A.C. 1130.

⁶⁹Lowendahl, 287 N.Y.S., p.74–75.

⁷⁰Piercing the Corporate Veil: Historical, Theoretical & Comparative Perspectives, Cheng-Han Tan, Jiangyu Wang, Christian Hofmann (2019), P.163.

⁷¹Adams v Cape Industries plc [1990], Court: Court of Appeal (England and Wales), 1990.

⁷²The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p. 400.

⁷³Ian M Ramsay & David B Noakes, Piercing the Corporate Veil in Australia, 19 Company and Securities Law Journal, 2001, p.9.

⁷⁴The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p. 402; Alexander Daehnert, 'Lifting the corporate veil: English and German Perspectives on Group Liability' 18 International Company and Commercial Law Review, 2007, p. 395.

⁷⁵The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p. 403; Sealy L, & Worthington's Cases and Materials in Company Law (10th edn. OUP Oxford 2013),

unit theory was specifically developed to address corporate groups⁷⁶. It was first introduced by **Lord Denning** in **DHN**⁷⁷, where he treated the corporate group as a single economic entity. However, his reasoning for treating the three companies as one entity was thin, and he provided no clear guidance on when the theory should apply. Moreover, because **D.H.N.** was a compensation case, its relevance to shareholder liability remained unclear.

Although, the single economic unit theory has been repeatedly criticized⁷⁸, the theory has continued to appear in English veil-piercing decisions, including **Cape Industries and others**⁷⁹. In **Cape**⁸⁰, which concerned tort liability, claimants argued that the group functioned as a single economic unit because Cape controlled its Subsidiaries and effectively ignored corporate formalities. While the court accepted much of the factual background, it held that the Subsidiaries had been properly constituted and that corporate forms were respected. As a result, Cape and its Subsidiaries remained distinct legal entities, and the veil was not pierced.

This case suggests that the “single economic unit” argument is unlikely to succeed as a basis for piercing the corporate veil and holding a Holding company liable for its subsidiaries’ debts. This highlights some inconsistency in judicial reasoning, since courts generally uphold the principle of separate legal personality, but in some cases, they consider the practical realities of how corporate groups operate⁸¹.

Conclusion

The doctrine of piercing the corporate veil actually strengthens - rather than weakens - the principle of limited liability. Limited liability exists to reduce investment risk by allowing Holding companies to operate through Subsidiaries without exposing themselves to direct liability. However, when a Holding company fails to respect the Subsidiary’s separate legal identity - treating it merely as an alter ego or instrumentality - it may lose that protection. In such cases, piercing the corporate veil reassures creditors and other interested parties that the Subsidiary operates as a distinct legal entity, with its own capital structure and management. This builds trust, ensures proper corporate governance, and allows courts to hold the Holding company directly liable if the Subsidiary’s separate status is abused.

p.69; Challenging the Limited Liability of Parent Companies: A Reform Agenda for piercing the corporate veil, Helen Anderson, 22 Australian Accounting Review, 2012, p.129, 133.

⁷⁶DHN Food Distributors Ltd v Tower Hamlets London Borough Council, 1 WLR 852, 1976, p.860; Laurence Gower, Modern Company Law 216 (3d. ed. 1979).

⁷⁷DHN Food Distributors Ltd v Tower Hamlets London Borough Council, 1 WLR 852, 1976, p.850, D.H.N. notwithstanding, English judges have asserted on various occasions that there is no presumption that group companies be treated as a single economic unit or an enterprise under English company law.

⁷⁸ Karen Vandekerckhove, Piercing the Corporate Veil, 2007, p.72.

⁷⁹ Adams v. Cape Indus. plc, 1990, Ch. 433 (A.C.), p. 532–539 (Eng.); In re Polly Peck Int’l plc, 2 All E.R. 433, Walker J., 1996, p. 447–448.

⁸⁰ Adams v Cape Industries plc, Court: Court of Appeal (England and Wales), 1990.

⁸¹The extent of a Holding company's liability for damages resulting from the faults of its subsidiaries, Dr. Rawi Mohamed Abdel Fattah Foley, Assistant Professor, Department of Commercial Law, Faculty of Law, Assiut University, p. 404.